

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982

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Bosh muharrir:
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

*Elektron nashr. 1303 sahifa.
E'lon qilishga 2024-yil 7-noyabrda ruxsat etildi.*

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Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

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O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

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REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Ensuring environmental security is of paramount importance in the broader context of national security, as it includes a set of activities, processes, and actions aimed at maintaining environmental balance and protecting nature and human well-being. According to B. Kutsyuruba and colleagues (2015), creating conditions for environmental safety ensures the protection of important interests of the individual, society, state, and environment from potential harm or threats emanating from human influence or technology. N. Panwar and colleagues (2011) define environmental safety as a state in which the natural environment and public health are not under immediate threat. This includes the protection of human rights, material and spiritual interests, natural resources, and the environment, serving as the basis for the development of the state and society.

In a global context, the Sustainable Development Goals, as noted by S. Parkin (2000), serve as a universal call to action, supported by countries of all economic statuses. These goals are aimed at improving well-being and preserving the planet, recognizing that the eradication of poverty must be accompanied by measures to address environmental, educational, health, social, and employment problems, including the fight against climate change. This perspective is also supported by N. Alfirevich and colleagues (2023) and R. Mori Jr. and colleagues (2019).

Sustainable development is based on several key components, including economic growth, social protection, environmental safety, spiritual and moral revival, institutional reforms, and improvement of the legal framework, state, and social construction. These components are interconnected and complement each other, playing an important role in achieving sustainable development.

Economic growth is a key element of sustainable development, which must be achieved through sustainable, cost-effective, and environmentally sound approaches, especially in the energy sector. It should be based on the principles of a green economy, encouraging the adoption of advanced, environmentally friendly technologies in all sectors. R. Owen and colleagues (2018) and G. Semeniuk and colleagues (2021) emphasize that adequate funds must be allocated for health, environmental protection, integrated resource management, and pollution control. The transition to a green economy is necessary to achieve sustainable development and social stability.

Social protection is another important aspect of sustainable development, requiring measures to reduce poverty, preserve human health and well-being, promote regional sustainability, and integrate strong environmental requirements into social and economic decision-making. M. Alexandrova (2020) and Cho and colleagues (2012) highlight that it is necessary to determine social support measures depending on the ecological zone and take into account the environmental conditions and health of the population of specific regions.

Environmental safety plays a key role in maintaining the well-being of ecological systems, including the atmosphere, water bodies, land areas, fauna, and flora. A. Kovacs and colleagues (2021) and N. Muradov and T. Veziroglu (2008) argue that these systems are interconnected and interdependent. Negative impacts on any of the components can have far-reaching consequences for the entire ecosystem. Achieving environmental safety requires an integrated approach, including forecasting, planning, and management, minimizing negative impacts on people, and balancing economic growth, industrial development, agriculture, and other sectors of the economy.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology employed qualitative and quantitative approaches. Primary data were collected through interviews and surveys with environmental experts and policymakers, providing insights into sustainability challenges and opportunities in Uzbekistan. Secondary data were sourced from academic journals, government reports, and international databases, focusing on recent studies. Data analysis involved thematic coding for qualitative insights and statistical methods to assess trends and impacts, ensuring a thorough understanding of sustainability priorities and supporting actionable recommendations.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

To ensure environmental safety, a new approach to economic mechanisms governing environmental management is also required. Currently, there are no integrated approaches and strategic planning in the field of environmental protection, and the powers of environmental authorities to effectively carry out their tasks are insufficient. The impacts of human activities, reflected in indicators such as public health, air quality, water standards and biodiversity, highlight the urgent need to improve economic mechanisms.

To achieve ecosystem sustainability within a market economy, an integrated approach is required that takes into account the complex interrelationship and interdependence of all components. This approach involves addressing key challenges to achieve our goals.

Stabilization of the environmental situation: We must work to stabilize environmental conditions by implementing measures that mitigate existing problems and prevent their further deterioration. This requires proactive steps to improve the environment, such as promoting green economic activities, introducing institutional and structural changes and moving towards a green economy.

Sustainable use of natural resources and combating environmental problems: to ensure the long-term conservation of our ecosystems, we must implement measures to sustainably manage use of natural resources, combating desertification and drought, effectively managing waste management, adopting safe practices in handling toxic chemicals, implementing environmentally friendly agricultural practices and adapting to the impacts of climate change.

Encouraging sustainable economic activity: It is important to encourage economic activity that operates within the capabilities of our ecosystems. This can be achieved through the widespread introduction of energy and resource-saving technologies, as well as changes in consumer behavior patterns. In this way, we can achieve a balance between economic development and conservation of our natural resources.

Stopping ecosystem destruction and biodiversity loss: Protecting vulnerable ecosystems and preventing further loss of biodiversity must be high on our priorities. This includes creating favorable conditions for the functioning of ecosystems and expanding protected areas. Organizations such as the International Union for Conservation of Nature and the Convention on Biological Diversity play an important role in achieving these goals.

To further improve the management of our natural resources, the costs and benefits of proposed environmental policies need to be carefully analyzed, taking into account both short and long-term impacts (S. Ambek and R. Lanois, 2008). This comprehensive assessment must be integrated into programs and projects related to economic and social development, providing a deep understanding of our potential to use natural resources.

In addition, adopting a territorial and regional approach to nature management promotes more targeted and effective strategies. It is necessary to implement requirements that ensure strict adherence to environmental safety standards, treating environmental safety as equally important as national security, public welfare and personal safety.

To successfully achieve these goals, it is necessary to unconditionally implement the “Concept of environmental protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” (A. Tleuke et al., 2022) and the “Strategy for the transition to a green economy.” In addition, the restoration of a unified system for preparing an annual national report on the state of the environment and the use of natural resources in Uzbekistan is essential for monitoring progress and making informed decisions.

By adopting this harmonious approach and pursuing these strategies, we can contribute to the sustainability of ecosystems, promoting a harmonious balance between economic prosperity and environmental conservation.

To achieve sustainable development, it is critical to understand the different levels of environmental threats and their consequences. These threats can be divided into four levels: **global, regional, national and local**. At the global level, we face such problems as climate change, water depletion and pollution, loss of biodiversity, melting glaciers and the Aral Sea disaster (E. Lyubimtseva and R. Cole, 2006; A. Sorg et al., 2012). These issues are recognized by international organizations such as the UN, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) and the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD).

Moving to the regional level, we are faced with problems of transboundary pollution, challenges in the field of water resources, generation and accumulation of waste, desertification and natural and man-made disasters. Organizations such as the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) and the United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification address regional environmental threats.

At the national level, threats include water shortages and pollution, insufficient quality of drinking water, irrational use of natural and energy resources, land degradation, air pollution, impacts on the gene pool of flora and fauna, impacts on public health, and accumulation of industrial and household waste. , insufficient use of resource conservation technologies and an increased risk of collapses and landslides. In this regard, the World Health Organization (WHO), the United Nations Development Program (UNDP) and the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNID) are among the organizations that focus on national environmental threats.

Finally, at the local level, there are pollution problems in specific regions, such as cities and regions, air pollution from vehicle emissions, degradation of ecosystems in certain areas, and noise pollution in cities and industrial centers. The Ministry of Ecology, Environmental Protection and Climate Change of the Republic of Uzbekistan, regional and municipal environmental reports clarify these local environmental threats.

In the current era of rapid global change, sustainable development requires consideration not only of the physical aspects, but also of the spiritual and moral state of society, especially the younger generation. Uzbekistan has made significant strides in improving its legislative framework, promoting new environmental thinking and increasing environmental awareness among the population. The adoption of legislative provisions to protect environmental rights, restore and protect the environment and address environmental problems in the Aral Sea region reflects this progress.

However, ecology should not remain the prerogative of only the environmental community. It should become a philosophy of life accepted by government agencies, public associations and other institutions of civil society, by every citizen. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the National Strategy for Sustainable Development of Uzbekistan, and current environmental legislation emphasize the importance of developing environmental awareness at all levels of society.

Collecting reliable, evidence-based information is critical to a comprehensive assessment of environmental threats and careful analysis.

The introduction of a unified system for preparing an annual national report on the state of the environment and the rational use of natural resources in Uzbekistan is necessary. In addition, modern indicators should be developed to accurately assess environmental pollution and resource use.

To ensure the environmental safety of Uzbekistan, the following areas should be considered priority:

- Rational and integrated use of natural resources, including water, land, mineral and biological resources;
- Reducing environmental pollution to levels consistent with standards and regulations, and improving environmental and sanitary conditions;
- Comprehensive measures to restore and improve the environmental condition of vulnerable regions, such as the Aral Sea region;
- Access of the population to high-quality drinking water, food and medicine;
- Introduction of environmentally friendly and resource-saving technologies;
- Development of scientific and technical capabilities in the field of environmental sciences and technologies;
- Introduction of an economic mechanism that integrates environmental requirements into socio-economic decision-making;
- Creation of experimental ecological zones promoting sustainable development;
- Creation of a unified system for environmental monitoring, forecasting and information dissemination;
- Development of methodologies for assessing noise pollution, vibration and electromagnetic radiation;
- Strengthening services for monitoring and protection against transboundary environmental pollution;
- Prevention and mitigation of environmental disasters, emergencies and accidents;
- Improving the system of environmental education and training, culture and public awareness programs;
- Creation of a unified regional system of environmental safety in Central Asia;
- Deepening cooperation with the international community to solve environmental problems.

Prioritizing these areas will allow Uzbekistan to make significant progress in ensuring environmental well-being and sustainable development. Active participation in international efforts to address environmental issues is also critical to a comprehensive approach to global challenges.

The effective development of state institutions is an important component of sustainable development, which covers various aspects, ranging from social and economic-financial to international, political, legal, cultural, technical and environmental. Improving institutional governance requires the creation of a robust system of legislation and regulations that promote environmentally friendly practices and ensure their effective implementation (S. Pan et al., 2018).

To achieve effective governance of these institutions, relevant structures must continuously review their approaches and methods, remaining responsive to the changing needs of society and informed about best practices to meet development challenges. These proactive measures will enable the activation of public policies related to environmental safety. They include the prevention and mitigation of environmental threats, optimization and monitoring of the environmental situation, as well as strengthening the responsibility of ministries, departments, local authorities, public organizations and every citizen of the Republic of Uzbekistan for achieving sustainable development.

By taking these steps, relevant institutions can align their activities with global standards and effectively contribute to sustainable development. The World Bank, the Asian Development Bank and the United Nations Development Program emphasize the importance of improving institutional governance to achieve these goals, recognizing its key role in creating sustainable and environmentally conscious societies.

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Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Jtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokr ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2024. № 11

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"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

